

SUPPLEMENT 10. Chinese scientific names of the new genus, new species, new combinations and species complexes recognized in this study; Zhu & Bau (2024) is referred to for new combinations regarding *Ephemerocybe*.

Scientific Names	
Latin	Chinese
<i>Cantonopsathyra</i>	穗脆柄菇属
<i>Cantonopsathyra serendipita</i>	穗脆柄菇 (奇缘穗脆柄菇)
<i>Cantonopsathyra malayanus</i>	马来穗脆柄菇
<i>Cantonopsathyra trechisporus</i>	糙孢穗脆柄菇
<i>Parasola haizhuensis</i>	海珠近地伞
<i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i> complex	堪多脆柄菇复合群 (黄盖堪多脆柄菇复合群)
<i>Candolleomyces efflorescens</i> complex	锦簇堪多脆柄菇复合群
<i>Candolleomyces iqbalii</i> complex	伊氏堪多脆柄菇复合群
<i>Candolleomyces luteopallidus</i> complex	淡赭堪多脆柄菇复合群
<i>Candolleomyces rogueianus</i>	罗格堪多脆柄菇
<i>Candolleomyces rubrobrunneus</i> complex	红褐堪多脆柄菇复合群
<i>Candolleomyces singeri</i> complex	辛格堪多脆柄菇复合群
<i>Candolleomyces typhae</i> complex	香蒲堪多脆柄菇复合群
<i>Ephemerocybe allovela</i>	异幕速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe amphithalla</i>	多宗速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe angulata</i>	角孢速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe aokii</i>	小褐速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe bisporiger</i>	双梗速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe bispora</i>	双孢速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe brevisetulosa</i>	短毛速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe callina</i> var. <i>callina</i>	径边速亡鬼伞原变种
<i>Ephemerocybe callina</i> var. <i>miionis</i>	径边速亡鬼伞塞地变种
<i>Ephemerocybe canistri</i>	织篮速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe christianopolitana</i>	克地速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe cinereopallida</i>	灰白速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe cinnamomeotincta</i>	桂色速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe congregata</i>	集生速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe doverii</i>	多弗速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe euryspora</i>	宽孢速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe fallax</i>	奇异速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe fuscocystidiata</i>	褐囊速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe heterosetulosa</i>	异毛速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe heterothrix</i>	异丝速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe hiascens</i>	假速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe impatiens</i>	凤仙速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe marculenta</i>	灰糠速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe maritima</i>	海滨速亡鬼伞

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SUPPLEMENT 10. (continued)

Scientific Names

Latin	Chinese
<i>Ephemerocybe minutispora</i>	小孢速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe mitrinodulispora</i>	钟瘤孢速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe pallida</i>	淡色速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe pellucida</i>	半透速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe plagiopora</i>	斜孢速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe pseudoamphithalla</i>	拟多宗速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe pseudodisseminata</i>	拟白小速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe radicella</i>	长根速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe sabulicola</i>	沙生速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe sassii</i>	塞斯速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe sclerocystidiosa</i>	硬囊速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe singularis</i>	单生速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe subdisseminata</i>	亚白小速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe subimpatiens</i>	亚凤仙速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe subpurpurea</i>	近紫速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe uljei</i>	巫氏速亡鬼伞
<i>Ephemerocybe velatopruinata</i>	绒幕速亡鬼伞